

A SYSTEM FOR DEVELOPING THE PHYSICAL FITNESS OF YOUNG BASKETBALL PLAYERS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada basketbol mashg'ulotlari orqali jismoniy rivojlanishi va jismoniy tayyorgarligi darajasini yaxshilashga haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена информация о том, как улучшить физическое развитие и физическую форму посредством тренировок по баскетболу.*

Abstract. *This article provides information on how to improve physical development and physical fitness through basketball training.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tezkorlik, sport, basketbol, interaktiv, chaqqonlik, tezkor harakat aniqligi.*

Ключевые слова: *Скорость, спорт, баскетбол, интерактив, ловкость, быстрота, точность движений.*

Keywords: *Speed, sports, basketball, interactive, agility, quickness, accuracy of movement.*

RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY.

Improvement of social, physical education and sports, promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population, creation of necessary conditions for field equipment and physical education are being implemented in the republic.

Decision PQ-5280 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 5, 2021 "Development of the activities of sports and educational institutions until 2025" implements specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population in the field of physical education and sports. to attract young people to sports and to select talented athletes from among them, to form national teams with skilled athletes who provide high results in sports, and additional conditions for coaches that there is a need to create and identify talented athletes by holding "Children's Sports Games" among sports school students-athletes and create reserves for youth national teams, select young athletes and select talented athletes for major sports (selection), the tasks of establishing a system of forming a sports reserve are defined as priority tasks.

The purpose of the study: To improve the physical fitness of young basketball players and increase their interest in sports through an interactive method.

Research tasks: Achieving this goal was carried out on the basis of the following tasks.

To study the level of physical development of young basketball players engaged in the initial training stage; to determine the physical fitness of young basketball students of general education schools by using folk action games, and to draw certain conclusions by observing the development process

- to determine the effective methods, forms and ways of educating students' physical qualities through the use of folk movement games in basketball sports training in secondary schools.

The object of the study: Jizzakh training center for Olympic and Paralympic sports is the physical development and preparation process of basketball players.

Subject of research: The use of action games in training young basketball players through the use of special exercises, their activity in the conditions of the formation of physical qualities, skills and abilities of students.

THE MAIN PART

Effective performance and high results in modern basketball can be increased only through highly developed physical training. The most important physical qualities for basketball players are strength, courage and endurance. It is these qualities that affect the effective performance of most game skills.

But this conclusion should not lead to the conclusion that other physical qualities are less important for basketball players. On the contrary, the ability to move quickly, to pass the ball over a long distance with power, and to be able to effectively perform long-term skills without reducing the ability to work, are in the leading position. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the qualities of speed, strength, agility, endurance and flexibility in sports training. Because the sufficiently developed of these qualities leads to the effective formation of sports skills. In other words, these qualities are the most necessary foundation for the rapid and perfect growth of sports skills.

It is known that a person is busy with activities such as play, study, work, and rest in his life. Education of the young generation growing up in our country is considered one of the most important tools for the formation of high moral and physical qualities of teenagers. In particular, the sport of basketball occupies an important place in the physical education of school-aged children, because this sport has a positive effect on the comprehensive improvement of movement skills, proper physical development, strengthening and maintenance of health.

Reforming the general education school, strengthening the education of the young generation,

It is related to the extremely important tasks of educating them in the spirit of community, hard work and fulfilling their duty to society. This means that from the first day of school, children are taught to love work, to be organized, to work hard, and to finish what they have started.

Junior school age is the initial period of formation of knowledge, skills and abilities, formation of imagination and concepts. At the same time, there are many opportunities for regular and consistent education of boys and girls. Sports play a special role in the education system of children of primary school age. In terms of discipline, attitude to work, children's character and abilities, and teaching methods, sports seem to be very different, even in the most favorable conditions.

Voluntary behavior develops in children of primary school age due to the formation of will. Work activities at school and at home, physical exercises and work activities at home, physical exercises will help in this. Sports play an important role in the physical, mental, moral and aesthetic development of young students. Raising children is as important as sports in their comprehensive development.

Agility, quickness, precision of movement, and observation of the appearance of balance are characteristic of young school age. In general, basketball is developing more and more. Nevertheless, it is possible to set a single system of purposeful use of the activities of students and youth. Studying these aspects, scientific theoretical analysis and production of educational and methodological manuals on the basis of practical suggestions is necessary.

Physical training of young athletes is considered one of the most important components of sports training and is understood as a process aimed at comprehensive development of the body, strengthening of health, improvement of physical abilities and creation of a solid functional base for all other types of training.

Modern sports make high demands on athletes' physical fitness.

This can be explained by the following factors:

1) The growth of achievements in sports always requires a new level of development of physical abilities from the athlete;

2) A high level of physical fitness is a necessary condition for increasing training and competition loads.

Physical training is divided into general physical training (GPF), auxiliary and special physical training (SPT) according to the nature and direction of the effect of the used tools.

General physical fitness of young athletes is the foundation and necessary basis for achieving high results. It is aimed at solving the following tasks:

- 1) increase the functional capabilities of the body of young athletes;
- 2) development of physical qualities - strength, quickness, endurance, dexterity and flexibility;
- 3) elimination of defects in the physical development of young athletes;

GPF includes a wide variety of tools; among them there are exercises performed with projectiles, in partnership, on special devices, various types of sports - acrobatics, athletics, sports games, speech and other general development exercises.

1. Auxiliary physical training of young athletes is aimed at creating a functional basis necessary for effective activity aimed at the development of special physical abilities. It has a special direction and is aimed at solving the following tasks:

development of the athlete's functional capabilities, manifested in movement activities specific to the chosen sport;

- 1) improvement of the organism's ability to withstand high-level special loads;
- 2) increasing the intensity of recovery processes;

Special physical training of young athletes (SPT) is aimed at the development of physical abilities in strict compliance with the requirements set by the characteristics of competition activities in the selected sport. Special physical training of young athletes solves the following tasks:

- 1) improvement of physical abilities specific to the chosen sport;
- 2) in-depth development of movement skills necessary for successful technical and tactical improvement in the chosen sport;
- 3) selective development of specific muscle groups that are more involved in performing specialized exercises.

SPT of young athletes is directed to the development of the most important movement qualities in the system of movement skills. Therefore, as the main means of special physical training, competition exercises are used together with various complicating elements that increase their effect on the athlete's body.

All types of physical training have certain similarities. Physical fitness of young athletes is closely related to sports specialty. Inadequate assessment of any type of physical training in the training process will ultimately prevent the development of sports skills. In the training of young athletes, the ratio of GPF and SPT tools is changed depending on the tasks, the age of the athletes, their qualifications, their special characteristics, the stages and periods of the training process, and the current state of the body. As the athlete's skill increases, the contribution of SPT means increases, and the volume of GPF means decreases accordingly.

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